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Nigeria Police Force and the Internal Security Challenges

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Abstract

Nigeria has recorded unprecedented internal security challenges, more than the external threat. The security challenges, such as the Boko Haram terrorism, banditry, secession, militancy, oil bunker and political violence, pose a threat to the peaceful coexistence of Nigeria. For instance, about 1.5 million people were either lost their lives and properties, or were displaced. However, the Nigerian constitution of 1999 established the Nigeria Police Force and charged it with the responsibility of maintaining law and order within the Nigerian geographical domain. Research indicates that a high rate of crimes overwhelmed the numerical strength of the Nigeria Police Force. Against this backdrop, this paper seeks to examine the role of the Nigeria Police Force in curtailing internal security challenges. Data were gathered from secondary sources. Realist theory is considered appropriate for the analysis of the research. Findings have shown that the Nigeria Police Force is faced with the challenges of a lack of manpower, lower remuneration, social welfare and inadequate accommodation.

Keywords: *Internal security challenge and Nigeria Police Force.*

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Nigeria Police Force and the Internal Security Challenges**Introduction**

Nigeria is bedevilled with security challenges that pose a threat to the survival of the country as a sovereign entity. The emergence of non-state actors, such as the Boko Haram terrorists, bandits, militants and secessionists, is a matter of great concern in Nigeria. The survival of Nigeria as an independent country is hinged on the numerical strength of its security institutions, and the commitment of the government and the citizenry in supporting the institutions with the necessary logistics that would enable them to discharge their constitutional responsibilities diligently. The Nigeria Police Force is a very large institution consisting of thirty-six State Commands and that of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), grouped into seventeen zones and eight administrative organs. Through its diverse functions and responsibilities as enshrined by the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria, the Nigeria Police Force is to uphold the rule of law, promote public safety, and uphold the rights and freedoms of all Nigerians. From the above explanation, three different structures in the Police Force can be identified. These are:

- a. Command (Authority) structure.
- b. Administrative structure
- c. Organisation structure.

These structures are patterned to meet the constitutional expectation of the police, to perform effectively the duties of maintenance of law and order, checkmating the excesses of criminals and ensuring peace and development in Nigeria.

The Nigeria Police Force is responsible for tackling internal security challenges as established by the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. However, the rapid increase in population of Nigerians, the emergence of new cities and the creation of

suburbs have led to an exponential increase in crimes and criminality in Nigeria. The situation became overwhelmed and undermined the internal security of Nigeria. Although much research has been conducted on the Nigeria Police Force, there is a paucity of data, especially on the Nigeria Police Force and internal security. This is mainly due to the sensitive nature of the topic and the unwillingness of the police authority to provide data on classified crimes and criminalities under investigation. Therefore, the methodology of obtaining data in this paper was largely from secondary sources, such as academic journals, books, magazines, newspapers and internet outlets.

The Nigeria Police Force, like other security agencies, is formally structured into commands and units. Undeniably, Muhammad (2021) explained that the Nigeria Police Force is under the command of the Inspector-General of Police, and any contingents of the Nigeria Police Force stationed in a State shall be subject to the authority of the Inspector-General of police, and be under the command of the Commissioner of police of that state. Against this background, this paper seeks to critically examine the role of the Nigeria Police Force in tackling internal security challenges.

Statement of Research Problems

The Nigeria Police Force has faced a range of challenges that impede its effectiveness in curtailing Nigerian internal crises. Some of the key problems include corruption, inadequate funding and resources, poor training and professionalism, community relations issues, lack of accountability, over-centralisation and lack of modern policing techniques. Many efforts have been made in order to tackle these problems, but the efforts have proved abortive. It is only when

modernity is introduced in the Nigeria Police Force, through the use of Information Communication Technology, that the Police Force will rise to meet expectations.

Theoretical Framework

Jacob (2012) defines theory as a set of ideas which explains a phenomenon. According to Jacob, a theory is expected to provide guidance, direction and explanation to phenomena in human society.

In light of the above definition, this paper has chosen realist theory as its frame of analysis. Realist theory or realism explains inherency and traces the root of conflict to a flaw in human nature, which is seen to be selfish and engaging in the pursuit of personalised self-interest that is defined as power. The theory originates from classical political theory and shares both theological and biological doctrines about an apparent weakness and individualism inherent in human nature. Thus, the starting point for the explanation of conflict is the individual level. Realists believe that “competitive processes” between actors, primarily defined as states, are the natural expression of conflict by parties engaged in the pursuit of scarce and competitive interests. This theory has three components: Descriptive Realism, which sees the world as arena of conflict; Explanatory Realism which seeks to show the world that there are genetic defects which push human kind into commission of crimes, and the crimes become inevitable because there is no mechanism to stop them from occurring; and Prescriptive Realism, which builds on arguments of Descriptive and Explanatory Realism which assert that decision makers have a moral justification to defend their territorial integrities and ensure safety of their citizens, using any means necessary (Ademola, 2014:45)

The above assumptions concurred with the objectives on which Nigeria Police Force is

established. The Nigeria Police Force is established to make Nigeria safer and more secure for economic development and growth: to create a safe and secure environment for everyone living in Nigeria. The objectives, however, are seen to be crashing; if observed, the degree to which crimes and criminalities are overwhelming the force to carry out its duties. This may not be unconnected with the insensitivity of those at the helm of affairs.

Literature Review

An Overview of Nigeria Police Force

Bakare and Ademola (2019) assert that the relative peace that placed Nigeria among the most secure nations in the West African sub-region has been eroded, and the country has suddenly metamorphosed into an abode of serial bombing, hostage-taking, kidnapping, armed robbery, cold-blooded murders and ethno-religious conflicts. The increasing nature of indices of insecurity in the country is not only disturbing but also questions the effectiveness of the Nigerian security architecture, especially that of the Nigeria Police, which is saddled with the responsibility of providing security to the people. Undeniably, the matter has triggered debates and counter-debates on how best to reposition the Nigeria Police Force to meet up with the dynamics of internal security challenges undermining peace and stability in the era of the challenge for the struggle for sustainable peace and the protection of lives and properties of Nigerians, is of great importance.

Sheriff (2017) argues that the Nigerian Police Force has, in various ways has championed the cause of societal development in all stratifications of Nigerian society. According to her, the police have identified corruption, insecurity, and often criminal activities as the major setbacks that adversely affected the peace, unity and progress of the country.

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Arguably, the above expression is characterised by judgmental opinions. The Nigeria Police is struggling with a plethora of challenges that include a shortage of manpower, poor financing, inadequate modern gadgets, poor remuneration and many more. In this context, therefore, the Nigeria Police needs urgent government attention to meet up with modern policing of crime prevention and crime detection. Manpower is essential in achieving the objectives for which the Nigeria Police is established. In this light, Muhammad (2021) explains that it is disturbing that Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa with a population of about 220 million people, has only 371,800 officers. The United Nations roughly establishes that global median of 300 police officers for every 100,000 civilians. While countries like China, India and the United States of America have about 1.6 million, 1,590,000 and 910,000 police officers, respectively.

According to Akull (2011), the Nigerian government has acknowledged the problems militating against the effective performance of the Nigerian Police Force as postulated above. In contemporary times, it appears there are growing efforts in ensuring the efficiency and effectiveness of the police force toward the maintenance of peace and security in Nigeria. For example, from the late 1990s to date, the Nigerian Police Force has embarked on several measures of fighting crime, some of which include: operation sweep, operation flush, operation fire for fire, anti-crime patrol, operation Dzenda, to mention a few, have been introduced. All these efforts are to ensure peace. Arguably, these efforts have not yielded the needed results of ensuring a crime-free Nigeria that could attract foreign direct investment. This brings about the critical quest to overhaul the entire Nigerian Police Force for efficiency, effectiveness and sustainable service delivery. Also, to meet the

demand of Nigerians for peace and a safe environment.

The Operation Fire for Fire Mechanism initiated by the former Inspector-General of Police, Tafa Balogun, has nonetheless yielded a positive result to some extent. For instance, the arrest of the notorious cross-border armed robber, Tijjani Hamani, the Police Force was able to checkmate the excesses of trans-border arms pushers. Also, the aim and objectives of the Operation Fire for Fire mechanism were to tackle the problems of militia groups such as the Movement for the Actualisation of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MOSSOB), Oodua People Congress (OPC), among others. The Operation “Puff Adder” was also launched on the 5th of April 2019 by the former Inspector-General of Police, Abubakar Muhammed Adamu, in the era of multiple security challenges. The operations have made some tremendous successes in dismantling cattle rustling, armed robbery, and kidnapping, to mention but few. But the operation suffers a series of challenges of poor funding, logistic insufficiency and lack of necessary tools for preventing and detecting crimes and criminalities.

Muhammad (2021) is of the view that most of the law enforcement agencies in Nigeria tend to give more priority to prevention and detection due to the great importance attributed to “crush a crime”. Instead of putting more effort into investigating crimes, the mechanism of ‘deterrence’ has proven to be more effective in maintaining public order in highly civilised societies. Indeed, crime prevention and detection are central to eliminating crimes and criminality. The centrality could only be attained if there is good governance with a coordinated economic system, the rule of law and a virile security system geared towards fighting crimes.

The Nature of Nigerian Internal Security Threats

Dunmoye (2012) has said that the contemporary Nigerian state is confronted with a dual crisis: the problem of legitimacy and the imperative of development. Nigeria's political economy is characterised by social, political and economic instability, conflicting social, regional, religious and ethnic interests, unbridled corruption, disrespect for the rule of law, ad-hoc policy formulation and inconsistent economic distribution rather than the generation of wealth. Superimposed on these are embarrassing failures of the security network as evidenced by wanton kidnappings, political assassinations, bombings and proliferation of small Arms light weapons. Since the return to democracy on 29th May 1999, the policing system has been diverted in favour of elites and their immediate family members, against the purview of protecting every citizen regardless of their gender, geographical affiliation, faith or status. This is detrimental not only to the deprived class of people but to the police force as a constitutional institution.

Ntim (2006) elucidates that the responsibility of the police is for internal security; that is, the maintenance of law and order in the state. When crises erupted in 1987, 1992, 1996, 2000 and 2002, the police were called upon to intervene. It is the duty of the State Commissioner of Police to inform the Governor, who is the Chief Security Officer of the State, about any crisis. The Governor, in turn, informs the President and Commander-in-Chief of the Nigerian Armed Forces of the situation. The President then advises the Governor accordingly.

The police, thereafter, move into the crisis areas to quell it. Depending upon the nature of the crisis, the police may initially do what is called a 'show of force' by firing into the air and using tear gas. When the police are

overstretched, the Armed Forces are now called upon to intervene. The police were a bit tardy in their response to the 1999 Kafanchan crisis between the Hausa community and the Ninzom and Kaninkon People.

Findings

In this context, the findings that originate from the results of the data were collected and analysed through the use of content analysis, as is the case in qualitative research. However, the findings indicate that;

- i. There is a link between manpower shortage in the Nigeria Police Force and the challenges faced in tackling internal security crimes and criminalities.
- ii. The Nigeria Police Force needs to be overhauled to meet the modern policing system.
- iii. That the government, citizens and other stakeholders should do whatever is constitutionally necessary for the Nigeria Police Force to discharge its responsibility.
- iv. The level of insecurity overwhelmed the police manpower. There is a need to employ committed and law-abiding Nigerians to strengthen its efforts.

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is no doubt that the degree of crimes and criminalities that are bedevilling Nigeria is daunting, and the numerical strength to curtail them is challenging. This may not be unconnected with the nature of the force as a former colonial legacy, which was driven by British imperial interest. The first Police institution was established by the Former British colonial Governor General, Sir Lord Lugard, in October 1861 (Sheriff, 2017). It is against this background that the Nigeria Police Force needs to undergo a series of reforms to meet the new wave of internal security challenges. The Nigeria Police Force

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needs a rebranding mechanism to change public perception of it. In the quest to tackle internal security challenges in Nigeria, through the use of the Nigerian Police Force, the following recommendations have been forwarded:

- i. The remuneration of the Police Force should be reviewed upward to conform to the current economic hardship. The government should uphold the standard of the Nigeria Police Force to conform to the modern policing system. The cross-border migration should be checked to avert the effect of external forces, which in most cases constitute threats internally.
- ii. The law-abiding Nigerians should imbibe the culture of reporting any person with questionable character. The Nigeria Police Force needs to be empowered with sophisticated security gadgets that could enable it to conduct smooth prevention and detection of crimes and criminality in Nigeria.
- iii. The number of Security challenges is daunting for the Police Force to tackle. There is a need for the Police Force to synergise with other sister security agencies, such as the Nigerian Armed Forces, Nigerian Customs Service (NCS), Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS) and the Vigilante Services.

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